

Research

A study of Econometric linkage between SHRM practices and performance of the organization

Summra Khalid^{1*}, Wang Dan²

¹Research Scholar, Department of business administration, Liaoning Technical University, Fuxin, china

²PhD supervisor, faculty member of Liaoning Technical University, Fuxin, china

*Corresponding author

summrakhalid84@gmail.com

Accepted: 23 October, 2020; Online: 25 October, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4130706>

Abstract: Empirical relationship between Human resource practices and performance of the organization has been tested in this research paper. Empirical evidence of positive association between organization performance and Human Resource Management (HRM) has been published however it is difficult to demonstrate a causal link. It has provided mix findings as some empirical research has tried to shed more light on these issues. A field survey using questionnaire was conducted to test the preposition. The main mass of our sample is consisting on public and private sector organization's employees. Employees who are actively involved in working life had been included in convenient sampling method and these forms were handled to those employees. From Lahore region a total of 450 questionnaires, 174 were timely returned and replied and 140 were able to include in our analysis. For the purpose of hypothesis testing ANOVA single factor was applied to test the significance level between variables and further significance was tested on results of ANOVA by applying t-test statistics. ANOVA single factor shows that all variables are statistically significant with each other and t-test further verified that the significance is not present between performance, business strategy and performance appraisal values. All other variables are statistically significant with performance of the organizations.

Keywords: Performance, Business strategy, Learning objectives, Performance appraisals, Training and development, leadership skills

Introduction

Empirical evidence of positive association between organization performance and Human Resource Management (HRM) has been published however it is difficult to demonstrate a causal

link (Combs, Liu, Hall and Ketchen 2006; Boselie, Dietz and Boon, 2005; Guest, Michie, Conway and Sheehan 2003). About the direction of the causality, this is largely because insufficient methodologies rigor in analysis limit inferences (Shedish, Cooke and Cambell 2002). When HRM procedures are introduced, it is difficult to know or by whom (Guest 2011). It has provided mix findings as some empirical research has tried to shed more light on these issues. Between HRM practices and organization performance indicators, some studies have reported a significant simultaneous and longitudinal relationship (Sheehan 2014, Wright and Boswell 2002 and Becker and Gerhart 1996). Suggesting that past performance is a much stronger predictor of current performance and overtake any impact of HRM, other studies found that initially HRM leads to better organization performance but this link disappear once past performance is controlled (Guest et al 2003).

Wright, Gardner, Moynihan and Allen (2005) studies assessing the relationship between multiple HR practices and performance of the organizations, they studied 68 researchers and summarized four types of designs among empirical studies, these designs were predictive, post predictive, retrospective and contemporaneous designs of research. Within HR performance designs the post predictive research design is far the most prevalent design. HRM practices are measured after the performance period in this design (Black and Lynch 2001). To recall HR practices that exist prior to the performance period, survey practices are asked in retrospective research design. Guthrie (2001) while asking respondents during that time to report the practices that exist during 1995/6 uses performance data from 1996/7. Delery and Doty (1996) use HR practices data during 1992 and year end performance data is the estimation because contemporaneous methodology use contemporaneous HR practices and performance data. It is difficult to draw a organization and reliable cause and effect relationship since the year end data encompasses performance from months prior to and concurrent with HR practices measure. Predictive studies are only classified in less count; the extent to which HRM practice assessed at one point in time can influence organization performance in predictive studies at later point in time can be assessed.

Snell and Youndt (1995) is the best example that relates HR practices to performance of three years with (Youndt, Snell, Dean and Lepak 1996).

Materials and methods

A result of organizations strategic management tendency is the emergence of strategic human resource management. To achieve higher organizational performance all business functions try to link their work methods and practices with organization strategy in today's management practices. Strategic human resource management emerge when human resource department try to harmonize their strategies, practices with organization strategies and processes as it is stated by Miles and Snow (1984). HRM stay as a functional process in the organization if you do not observe such a link between HRM and organization strategies.

Sustainable competitive advantage derived from a organization's physical, organizational and human resource base (Colbert 2004). Judgment intelligence, experience, training, employees in an organization, relationships and insight of individual managers included in human capital resources and these components are considered important for the achievement of competitive advantage with effect of value creating strategies (Barney 1991). So proved that strategic human resource is naturally affiliated with the resource based views of the competitive advantage and the integration of the resource based views of the organization into strategic human resource management (Wright, Dunford and Snell 2001). Colbert (2004) studied that the perception of the resource based views serves the strategic human resource management field in these two ways: 1) the resource based views prompted HRM research on leveraging human capital. 2) If employees are reflected through positive attitudes and behaviors such as commitment and job satisfaction, the employee's characteristics add values to the organization.

Strategic Human resource management and organization performance relationship is divided into two perspectives, first is the macro focus on the overall or slandered set of human resource management practices and the performance of the organization (Huselid and Becker 1996; Huselid, Jeckson and Schuler 1997). Second is a strategic perspective on human resource management that emphasis the particular fitness between various Human resource practices and competitive edge as explained by (Storey 2011). Rather than investigating the effect of the individual HRM practices on employee or organization performance, the former view is related

to a system view of HRM and considered the overall configuration or aggregation of HRM practices and policies (Bowen and Ostroff 2004).

Human resource management and performance of the organization research mainly applied two different approaches of strategic human resource management, the contingency approach and the universalistic or best practice approach. As HRM can provide a sustainable competitive advantage for the organization so both perspectives stress on it.

Research Methodology

The researcher aims to identify the mediating effect on the relationship between organizational factors like strategic human resource management practices and organization performance. A field survey using questionnaire was conducted to test the proposition. The questionnaire was only administered to the participants who are currently employed in organizations. Six performance based questions were asked from participants these questions were:

- Performance is always depended on human resource practices
- Business strategy must need to be communicated for best performance
- Employees should know what they need / Learning Objectives for best performance
- Performance appraisals must be known to employee
- Training and development directly impact the performance of the organization
- Performance built leadership skills

The main mass of our sample is consisting on public and private sector organization's employees. To collect data associated with the variables in the research a printed questionnaire was created. Employees who are actively involved in working life had been included in convenient sampling method and these forms were handled to those employees. From Lahore region a total of 450 questionnaires were collected, a 7 options scale was presented to the respondents, they were allowed to conduct evaluations regarding each entry (1= strongly disagreed and 7= strongly agreed). One way ANOVA and t-test was performed to test the hypothesis that checked the significance of the variables. Out of 450 questionnaires 174 were timely returned and replied and 140 were able to include in our analysis.

Hypothesis

H_0 =Variables used in survey questionnaires are not statistically significant with each other

H_1 =Variables used in survey questionnaires are statistically significant with each other

For the purpose of hypothesis testing ANOVA single factor was applied to test the significance level between variables and further significance was tested on results of ANOVA by applying t-test statistics.

Data analysis

There are seven questions in questionnaire, asking participants about the performance, business strategy, learning objectives of the business, performance appraisal, and building of leadership skills by performance and income of the employees. Other than income of the employees, all factors were asked from the participants upon which they given their views selecting options from seven point likert scale. On the other hand participants were categorized on two basis, male and female: male participants given the number of dummy variable 1 and female participants represented by 0. Selection of option 7 means highly agreed and selection of option 1 means disagree on the comment.

Mean deviation shows that the performance is dependent on human resource practices. Its value of average is 4.70, which is high among all other variables. Means to say participants are more agreed upon this argument. This results match with the research of (Hall and Ketchen 2006: Boselie, Dietz and Boon, 2005). They also showed that human resource management is positively correlated with the performance of the organization. Other two factors of importance are performance appraisal and communication of business strategy with the employees, learning objectives and building of leadership skill by performance have lower mean deviation.

Going towards the sum of values, its more in performance, than performance appraisal and business strategy as correlated with these values with average, participants are more satisfied on these points. Upon the number of gender, male were assigned the number of 1, and female repressed by 0, so her 102 means that these are men and other 38 participants were women.

Anova: Single Factor

SUMMARY

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Performance	140	658	4.7	3.434532
Business strategy	140	599	4.278571	4.360689
Learning Objectives	140	186	1.328571	0.509969
Performance appraisals	140	614	4.385714	4.123535
Invest in training	140	235	1.678571	1.428314
Performance built leadership skills	140	263	1.878571	1.402415
Gender	140	102	0.728571	0.199178
Income of employees	140	4160000	29714.29	1.62E+08

ANOVA

<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	1.08E+11	7	1.54E+10	760.7128	0.000	2.017799
Within Groups	2.26E+10	1112	20308070			
Total	1.31E+11	1119				

The most important explanation of the research is ANOVAs table, when setting up this analysis; here alpha was left at default level of 0.05. If the p value is less than alpha, than we can say that there are statistically significant differences between variables/ questions asked in survey. In this case p value is 0.00 which is less than 0.05; therefore this test indicates that we have statistically significant differences between variables. But the limitation upon this test is that we can make assumption upon these variables like: performance is statistically significant with communication of business strategy. Business strategy is statistically significant with learning objectives and so on.

Hypothesis testing

H_0 =Variables used in survey questionnaires are not statistically significant with each other.

H_1 =Variables used in survey questionnaires are statistically significant with each other.

So under this assumption, p value is less than 0.05 so we can accept the alternate hypothesis rejecting null hypothesis.

Two tailed t-test further verified the significance of the variables with performance, table below shows that how other variables are statistically significant with performance, p value of business strategy and performance appraisal is higher than alpha, but all other values (showing E) are less than 0.05 level of significant.

T-Test

Performance	Business strategy	P value	0.068607586
Performance	Learning Objectives	P value	6.31219E-44
Performance	Performance appraisal	P value	0.157175669
Performance	Invest in training	P value	9.26997E-34
	performance build leadership		
Performance	skills	P value	1.22939E-34
Performance	Gender	P value	2.30719E-52
Performance	Income of employees	P value	3.15144E-58

Conclusion

Hypothesis on the significance of the variables are tested by the ANOVA single factor and also with the t test statistics, ANOVA single factor shows that all variables are statistically significant with each other and t-test further verified that the significance is not present between performance, business strategy and performance appraisal values. All other variables are statistically significant with performance of the organizations.

References

1. Combs, J., Liu, Y., Hall, A., & Ketchen, D. (2006). How much do high-performance work practices matter? A meta-analysis of their effects on organizational performance. *Personnel Psychology, 59*, 501–528
2. Boselie, P., Dietz, G., & Boon, C. (2005). Commonalities and contradictions in HRM and performance research. *Human Resource Management Journal, 15*(3), 67–94.
3. Guest, D. E., Michie, J., Conway, N., & Sheehan, M. (2003). Human resource management and corporate performance in the UK. *British Journal of Industrial Relations, 41*(2), 291–314.
4. Shadish, W. R., Cooke, T. D., & Campbell, D. T. (2002). *Experimental and quasi experimental designs for generalized causal inference*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
5. Sheehan, M. (2014). Human resource management and performance: Evidence from small and medium-sized organizations. *International Small Business Journal, 32*(5), 545–570.
6. Snell, S. A., & Youndt, M. A. (1995). Human resource management and organization performance: Testing a contingency model of executive controls. *Journal of Management, 21*(4), 711–737.
7. Storey, D. (2011). Optimism and chance: The elephants in the entrepreneurship room. *International Small Business Journal, 29*(4), 303–321
8. Guest, D. E. (2011). Human resource management and performance: Still searching for some answers. *Human Resource Management Journal, 21*(1), 3–13.
9. Wright, C. F., & Boswell, W. R. (2002). Desegregating HRM: A review and synthesis of micro and macro human resource management research. *Journal of Management, 28*(3), 247–276.
10. Becker, B., & Gerhart, B. (1996). The impact of human resource management on organizational performance: Progress and prospects. *Academy of Management Journal, 39*, 779–801.
11. Wright, P. M., Gardner, T. M., Moynihan, L. M., & Allen, M. R. (2005). The relationship between HR practices and organization performance: Examining causal order. *Personnel Psychology, 58*, 409–446.
12. Black, S. E., & Lynch, L. M. (2001). How to compete: The impact of workplace practices and information technology on productivity. *Review of Economics & Statistics, 83*, 434–445.
13. Guthrie, J. P. (2001). High-involvement work practices, turnover and productivity: Evidence from New Zealand. *Academy of Management Journal, 44*, 180–190.
14. Delery, J. E., & Doty, H. D. (1996). Modes of theorizing in strategic human resource management: Tests of universalistic, contingency, and configurationally performance predictions. *Academy of Management Journal, 39*(4), 802–835.
15. Youndt, M. A., Snell, S. A., Dean, J. W., Jr., & Lepak, D. P. (1996). Human resource management, manufacturing strategy, and organization performance. *Academy of Management Review, 39*(4), 836–866.

16. Colbert, B. A. (2004). The complex resource-based view: Implications for theory and practice in strategic human resource management. *Academy of Management Review*, 29(3), 341–358.
17. Wright, P. M., Dunford, B. B., & Snell, S. A. (2001). Human resources and the resource based view of the organization. *Journal of Management*, 27, 701–721.
18. Huselid, M. A., & Becker, B. E. (1996). Methodological issues in cross-sectional and panel estimates of the HR-organization performance link. *Industrial Relations*, 35, 400–422.
19. Huselid, M. A., Jackson, S. E., & Schuler, R. S. (1997). Technical and strategic human resource management effectiveness as determinants of organization performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39, 949–969.
20. Bowen, D. E., & Ostroff, C. (2004). Understanding HRM-organization performance linkages: The role of the ‘strength’ of the HRM system². *Academy of Management Review*, 29, 203–221.
21. Miles, R. E. and Snow, C. C. (1984). Designing strategic human resources systems. *Organizational dynamics*, 13(1), 36-52.
22. Barney, J. (1991). Organization resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of management*, 17(1), 99-120.

Acknowledgments

I am grateful to all of those with whom I have had the pleasure to work during this and other related projects. I would especially like to thank Wang Dan.

Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

